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D.2.2 ARCHLAB Second Access Report

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Abstract

This document describes the activities of the ARCHLAB transnational access program carried out during the second period (M28-48) of the IPERION HS project.

In particular, the deliverable reports on the initiatives that have been taken to diffuse information on the ARCHLAB opportunities offered to users, on the announcement of calls for proposals, projects' selection by peer review, exploitations of the ARCHLAB infrastructure and the initiatives related to data management.

This deliverable was carried out with the partners of the consortium of WP2 that provided access and describes in more detail the projects implemented, the days of access, the objectives of the visits and the results achieved during the visits.

Table of contents

Document information	2
Abstract	3
Table of contents	4
List of figures and tables	5
Abbreviations	6
Introduction	7
ORGANISATION OF ARCHLAB	8
1. <i>START OF THE WORK</i>	8
2. <i>THE ARCHLAB PEER REVIEW PANEL (PRP)</i>	9
3. <i>PUBLICITY OF ACCESS AND CALLS FOR PROPOSALS</i>	9
4. <i>SUPPORT FROM THE ARCHLAB WELCOME DESK</i>	10
ARCHLAB ACCESS ACTIVITIES (M28-48)	10
KPI's	24
ADVANCING RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT IN ARCHLAB	27
CONCLUSION	28
References	32
ANNEXE	33

List of figures and tables

Figure 1: Map of ARCHLAB providers 7

Figure 2: ARC21_MURTECH, NIH, on site visits 29

Figure 3 ARC27_Durable Splendour_IPCE 29

Figure 4: ARC30_DASA_IPCE 30

Figure 5: ARC 34_SCC, archives NIH 30

Figure 6: ARC35_SIAB-REGIA, Historic England 31

Figure 7: ARC 44_VITAL Cu, Historic England 31

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
HS	Heritage Science
PRP	Peer Review Panel
Nr	Number
TNA	TransNational Access

Introduction

The ARCHLAB platform is an integrated system of 14 distributed facilities located in outstanding European museums and research centres in 9 countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, Romania, Spain, Sweden and the UK, see figure 1):

ARCHLAB_1: Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium/Institut Royal du Patrimoine artistique, Brussels, (KIK-IRPA), BE www.kikirpa.be

ARCHLAB_2: Koninklijk Museum voor Kunst en Geschiedenis/Musée Royal d'Arts et Histoire, Brussels, (KMKGMRAH), BE www.kmkg-mrah.be

ARCHLAB_3: Centre de Recherche et des Restauration des Musées de France and Laboratoire de Recherche de Monuments Historiques, Paris, (CNRS#C2RMF-LRMH), FR www.c2rmf.fr and www.lrmh.fr

ARCHLAB_4: Rathgen Forschungslabor Staatliche Museen zu Berlin – Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz, Berlin, (SPK), DE www.smb.museum.de

ARCHLAB_5: Opificio delle Pietre Dure, Firenze, (OPD), IT www.opificiodellapietredure.it

ARCHLAB_6: Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed, Amsterdam, (RCE), NL www.cultureelerfgoed.nl

ARCHLAB_7: University of Groningen (RUG) Groningen Institute of Archaeology (GIA), NL www.lcm.rug.nl

ARCHLAB_8: National Institute of Heritage (NIH), Bucharest, RO <https://patrimoni.gov.ro>

ARCHLAB_9: Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España (IPCE), Madrid, ES, <http://ipce.mcu.es>

ARCHLAB_10: The Craft Laboratory (CL), Department of Conservation, Faculty of Science, University of Gothenburg (Sweden), www.craftlab.gu.se

ARCHLAB_11: The British Museum, London, (BM) UK, www.britishmuseum.org

ARCHLAB_12: The National Gallery, London, (NG) UK www.nationalgallery.org.uk

ARCHLAB_13: Historic England Laboratory, Fort Cumberland, Portsmouth (HEL-FC) UK

Figure 1: Map of ARCHLAB providers

ORGANISATION OF ARCHLAB

1. START OF THE WORK

The work performed by the ARCHLAB providers within the first months of the project (the re-activation and widening up of the program, in order to widely diffuse information on the existing and new opportunities offered by the ARCHLAB access among potential users and, by this way, ensuring an effective execution of the service and a regular and appropriate run). This allowed the access activities during the second M28-48 reporting period to continue in an effective way.

The achievement of these objectives has been possible through the following working steps:

- 1) participation through WP8 in a harmonization of call for proposals and review processes to contribute to an integrated access approach ARCHLAB-FIXLAB-MOLAB
- 2) preparation and opening of calls for proposals
- 3) eligibility and feasibility of proposals uploaded in the dashboard
- 4) selection of proposals by PRP
- 5) information to applicants and organization of the users' visits.

The open archives of the 14 providers contain documentation on the examination of cultural heritage materials, execution technology, state of conservation, alteration processes of cultural and natural objects, etc., including historical and archaeological information, images, as well as technical and scientific data. In addition to the access to archives and technical data on cultural heritage objects, the platform provides access to collections such as reference samples, zooarchaeological, archaeobotanical, human skeletal, dendrochronological and archaeotechnology collections to support archaeological research held by some of the participating archives, which are useful for providing characteristic and comparative data for researchers. Furthermore, in some cases, additional analyses on these collections as well as on the samples from the users can be carried out, in order to obtain results that can be scientifically compared.

In the IPERION HS ARCHLAB platform, scientists, conservators, archaeologists, paleontologists, zoologists and curators in Europe can apply for transnational access to the archives of the infrastructures in a different country. They can carry out comparative or complementary studies related to the scientific research project on which they are working using the physical materials, files and databases held at the host infrastructures. An integral component of access to the infrastructures is the possibility to benefit from the knowledge of experts in the institution specialised in the specific field. The experts will contribute via consultation and to the interpretation of data. Access to these data opens the way for deeper and broader studies than the current ones, leading to more high-quality research.

General objective of ARCHLAB is to enable to study cultural and natural heritage in a deeper and wider way, opening perspectives for a better circulation of knowledge among researchers in heritage science, permitting an easier achievement of high-level results, avoiding duplications of measurements, and stimulating a deeper integration and wider cooperation among European institutions for the study and conservation of heritage. Furthermore, ARCHLAB enables the alignment of research activities between the user's group and the provider hereby offering opportunities for further networking activities.

2. THE ARCHLAB PEER REVIEW PANEL (PRP)

The scientific panel is in charge of / evaluates the users group proposals on the basis of common peer review criteria, worked out for the 3 platforms through WP8, ranking them and selecting the most appropriate and scientifically sound ones. The 3 PRP members are external experts, recognized for their expertise in the field of heritage science.

The ARCHLAB PRP is the committee in charge to referee the proposals submitted by the users in order to select them on the basis of the scientific merit following the principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality.

As approved by the Steering Committee the ARCHLAB PRP, is composed by:

Koen Van Balen,

Prof, Departement Civil Engineer, KULeuven, Belgium;

Petria Noble,

Head of Paintings Conservation, Conservation and restoration, Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam, The Netherlands; and,

Gerhard Eggert,

Professor of conservation and restoration of archaeological, ethnological and handicraft objects in the department art conservation restoration, Staatliche Akademie der Bildenden Künste Stuttgart, Germany.

3. PUBLICITY OF ACCESS AND CALLS FOR PROPOSALS

Aim of this work was to guarantee that information about the opportunities offered by ARCHLAB (and relative calls for proposals) reaches the widest audience, in order to ensure a fast establishment of a fluent service run and to increase the opportunities for users.

Access Area web pages

Information on opportunities offered by the ARCHLAB service and announcements of Calls for proposals were distributed through the ARCHLAB Welcome Desk of the Iperion HS website. The ARCHLAB page at the Welcome Desk contains general description of the scope of TNA, mentioning new and existing providers. The pages of the Welcome Desk further contain detailed instructions and guidelines necessary to formulate and submit a proposal, through the dashboard application. Information was also reported on general rules and modalities of Access, as: eligibility of users, modality of presentation of proposals, modality of selection, etc.

All ARCHLAB access providers were involved at all stages in the setting up of the ARCHLAB access pages and the announcement of the 3 calls enabling the announcement on their own website.

Other communication tools

In addition to the project website, the ARCHLAB Calls for proposals were announced via social media through WP8.

Since M28, three additional ARCHLAB calls (call 5 till call 7) have been announced up to month 48, with the following deadlines:

- call 5: 30/9/2022
- call 6: 28/2/223
- call 7: 30/6/2023

4. SUPPORT FROM THE ARCHLAB WELCOME DESK

As for the other transnational access platforms of IPERION HS, the Welcome Desk method was applied to ARCHLAB. The Desk consists of an integrated and relevant welcoming service - open for the overall project duration– offered by the ARCHLAB Helpdesk (Ineke Joosten, RCE) and the access provider’s research staff, responding to the user requests regarding technical and scientific information, feasibility of work, logistic aspects, etc., substantially supporting the users from the proposal preparation up to the exploitation of the visit.

An on-line Application System for the three platforms runs through an automated dashboard and includes a concise presentation of the research project, with a clear indication of the objectives and expected results, the foreseen duration of the access and desired period. A clear indication of the facility or the facilities to which it is requested to accede, must be indicated. At the end of each call, the WP Leader carries out a general check of the scope of ARCHLAB and quality of the proposals, follows up the eligibility and feasibility check, organizes the peer review and adapts the information in the dashboard accordingly.

ARCHLAB ACCESS ACTIVITIES (M28-48)

22 projects were received during the last 3 calls, of which 1 was rejected, due to ineligibility issues or too low quality. 21 proposals have been submitted to the Peer Review Panel, out of which 16 have been selected corresponding to 29 accesses (some proposals requested access to archives of more than one provider).

From the start of the project up to month 48, in total (table 1), 42 projects were received of which 3 were rejected, due to ineligibility issues or too low quality. 37 proposals have been submitted to the Peer Review Panel, out of which 29 have been selected corresponding to 44 accesses (some proposals requested access to archives of more than one provider).

Table 1: summary of the selection activities during the reporting period (ARCHLAB); reviewing process by the PRP is through email.

Call (final date)	Number of received proposals	Number of rejected proposals *	Date sending proposals to PRP	Submitted number	Countries	Date final ranking and selection	Selected number
1st (31 Jan 2021)	7	0	27 Febr 2021	7	IT, PT	27 March 2021	5
2nd (30 June 2021)	2	0	21 August 2021	2	F, GB, IT	11 Sept 2021	2
3rd (30 Nov 2021)	6	2	15 Jan 2022	3 ⁽¹⁾	DE, F, NL	12 Febr 2022	2
4rd (30 April 2022)	5	0	1 June 2022	4 ⁽²⁾	BE, IT, DE	27 June 2022	4
5th (30 Sept 2022)	4	0	31 October 2022	4	BE, CH, GB, HK, IT	3 December 2022	3
6th (28 Febr 2023)	4	1	25 March 2023	3	F, NL, RO	15 April 2023	1
7th (30 June 2023)	14	0	10 July 2023	14	AT, BE, CZ, DE, FR, IT, MD, NL, PT, RO, RS, TR	22 August 2023	12
Total number	42	3		37			29

(1): 1 project AORUM was already submitted in call 2 and re-submitted in call 3

(2): ARC20_Oddy-Torium was re-submitted with only a difference in user group composition and not re-submitted to the PRP

The origin of the selected proposals within call 5 to 7 is quite representative of the European diversity, with a panel of 12 nationalities, besides Switzerland and HongKong.

For the entire project (M1-M48), of the 29 selected proposals and 44 access visits, 37 access visits have been carried out corresponding to 163 access days. The number of access days (163) is below the objective of 341 access days at M48 (48%).

The table 2 gives an overview of the user-projects. The projects corresponding to the period M1-27 are marked in grey.

Table 2: overview of user-projects

Name user leader	Nr of users	Project acronym	Objectives	Infrastructure	Nr access (days)	Work carried out
First call						
Francesco Grazzi		ARC2_CO MABS		ARCHLAB 13_HE		<i>Cancelled</i>
Vanessah Antunes	1	ARC3_ZAINTIBERIA	The aim of ZAINTEBERIA: Zurbarán sAints PaINtings and its Technical Influence BEaring Iberian Art is to deepen our knowledge provided by 2019 IPERION CH access to IPCE under the theme SINPOS: Spanish INfluences in Portuguese Óbidos workShop. In this mission, we could identify technical aspects of Zurbaran painting practices, particularly concerning ground layers.	ARCHLAB 9_IPCE	5	Vanessa Antunes is focused on the study of Josefa de Óbidos, the most important female painter in Portugal from s XVII. Josefa de Obidos was born in Seville, where her father, Baltazar Gomes Figueira , was working with the Spanish painter Zurbarán. IPCE has deeply studied along the years the majority of Zurbarán paintings most of them from Guadalupe Monastery and the Fine Arts Museum in Seville. The visit was specially orientated to the Zurbaran ground layers, guarded in the Heritage samples IPCE Archive, in order to find similarities and better understand the technology in the Portuguese painter. YouTube video: https://youtu.be/jbkOwb2gHGY
Nicoletta Palladino	1	ARC4_ZOZOM	The project aims at the investigation of zinc white. An objective of the ARCHLAB visit was to find historical materials for analysis and archive sources for mock-ups preparation (e.g., paint recipes, artists' notes).	ARCHLAB _6 (RCE)	2	The archives were checked for the presence of zincwhite. Many reports were found and studied. In addition, several paint tubes and reference materials were sampled. Presentation of the project and discussions with RCE scientists on zinc white.
Marco Cardinali	1	ARC5 Imago	IMAGO aims to retrace the roots of Technical Art History, reaching in archives having pioneering	ARCHLAB 1_KIK-IRPA,	2	During his stay at KIK-IRPA, the user searched in the archives of Paul Coremans to seek the origins of material technical research within the period 1930.

	1		work of art historians and scientists in the period 1920-1930 in both the USA and Europe.	ARCHLAB 3_C2RM F	4	Mr Cardinali consulted the archives of the prefiguration of our research laboratory, from the time of Cellierier (1927-1929). These are the first experiments of scientific imaging in France, on paintings of the Louvre (photographs in direct light, UV, X-rays, examination under monochromatic filters). We also provided him with a private archive, that of the restorer Jean-Gabriel Goulinat, who created this laboratory with Cellierier. In addition, he was able to consult the EROS database and analyze X-ray images, in order to make comparisons between analyses from different periods.
	1			ARCHLAB 9_IPCE	2	For IPCE access was focused in the identification between Giorgione and Tiziano. For that, Mr. Cardinali was accessing three partial radiographies from the painting “virgin with Child between Saint Antonio de Padua and Saint Roque” s. XVI, realized by IPCE in the late sixties, beginning of the seventies.
	1			ARCHLAB 12_NG	3	Two particular areas of interest that the user hoped to address through access to the National Gallery archives were the contribution of Alan Burroughs from the Fogg Art Museum, Mass. USA, and the impact of the first international conference on the scientific examination of artworks in Rome in 1930. At the National Gallery the user was able to study a considerable number of x-ray images made by Burroughs of National Gallery paintings during his x-ray campaign in European museums in the late 1920s. The user was interested in how Burroughs was using these studies to investigate – among other questions - the distinction between Giorgione and the young Titian; with this in mind he consulted the conservation and scientific dossiers on paintings by these artists, to look at especially the early scientific studies of their materials and technique. He also found much material of interest in the National Gallery archives that related to the history of the use of scientific methods to examine paintings at the National Gallery, mainly from the mid-1940s onwards.
Angela Cerasuolo	1	ARC6_CA MPUS	Capodimonte Museum Proposal of User access for the study of Raphael technique process aims to examine the technical data on the works of Raphael in France to compare them with those of the paintings of Capodimonte.	ARCHLAB 3_C2RM F	5	Angela Cerasuolo consulted several dozen files of works by Raphael and his workshop (digital files on the EROS database, paper files, X-rays)

Second call						
Francesca Gherardi		ARC9_ART DEICS		ARCHLAB 6_RCE		<i>cancelled</i>
Romain Thomas	3	ARC10_AORUM	Analysis of gold and its uses as a painting material, end 15th – mid-17th c. Their research project focussed on the use of gold in European paintings from the end of the fifteenth century to the middle of the seventeenth century, meaning in the period after the heyday of gold ground paintings, when the use of gold began to be less common.	ARCHLAB 12_NG	3	Before their visit the user group had compiled a long list of National Gallery paintings they wished to study. At the Gallery they were able to study a range of scientific images and data to be able to compile information about the distribution of gold across a painting and also the technique with which it was applied, including details deriving from scientific analysis such as the chemical composition of a mordant used to adhere the gold. The paintings studied were very varied in their geographical origin, including works from France, Spain, the Netherlands, Germany, Italy and Portugal.
Third call						
Simon Steger	1	ARC14_Oddy-Torium	To test conservation materials for their atmospheric corrosivity for the protection of cultural artefacts	ARCHLAB 11_BM		<i>Cancelled and reintroduced in call 4</i>
Romain Thomas	4	ARC15_AORUM	To search for any easel painting, whatever its support (wood, canvas, stone or copper), whatever its technique (tempera, oil...) where the painter has used gold. In addition to gather as many pieces of information as possible about the gilding technique(s) employed by the painter in those paintings.	ARCHLAB 5_OPD	4	Selection of paintings to determine the gilding techniques in use. The state of conservation, the potential effect of alteration, or past restoration interventions on the gilding were evaluated. Collection of chemical and physical data, such as the composition (gold or composite alloy) and the nature of the gilding support (adhesive between the foil and the painting substrate)
	4			ARCHLAB 6_RCE	3	Consultation of the documentation concerning the analyses, the books with all the cross-sections, and the complete scientific reports of analyses of some artworks. Discuss with the RCE team, present the project in detail. A SEM analysis was done on a selected sample (see Error! Reference source not found.)

	4			ARCHLAB 12_NG	2	The user group who visited the National Gallery for arc_10 AORUM requested a second ARCHLAB access visit, as the first had been so fruitful that they felt that the NG documentation archives would be a valuable resource for further study on the same subject. Exceptionally, NG were also able to arrange for close study of some of the paintings themselves by the users in the storage area (AORUM). The users then also took the opportunity to study further scientific files beyond those consulted during the first visit, paying particular attention to certain gilding techniques prevalent in these later paintings, such as shell gold, which seems to have been favoured by certain artists.
Marya Albrecht	2	ARC16_EM PTY	The project entails the conservation and material-technical analysis of <i>The Madonna Enthroned surrounded by angels</i> attributed to Joan Reixach (collection Foundation de Haar, Utrecht). This painting dates from the mid-15th century and is painted on a wooden panel. The painting consists of two sections separated by carved tracery. The lower part shows Mary seated on a throne with Jesus on her lap. They are surrounded by singing angels, of which two offer vases of lilies to Mary and child. The upper part shows the crucified Christ with the three Mary's on the left. On the right St. John the Evangelist is depicted, together with a small crowd of people on the far right. A walled city is painted in the background. Spanish art of the 15th century is extremely rare in The Netherlands. This painting is one of very few examples in Dutch public collections.	ARCHLAB 9_IPCE	3	It is important for the continuation of the conservation treatment to understand how the degraded areas might have looked originally. Research on other paintings by the same artist or contemporaries is necessary, and this is the reason of IPCE access in order to look at technical data present in its archives. See Error! Reference source not found. YouTube video: https://youtu.be/j3_E5Gr2it8
Fourth call						
Francisco De Mederos	2	ARC17_ME TOX IT	To compare metal oxalates formation in Italian oil paintings to North European ones	ARCHLAB 5_OPD	6	Selection of a corpus of oil samples in cross-sections for FTIR mapping and Raman analysis to check the presence and distribution of metal oxalates

Maria Cristina Tomasetti	2	ARC18_Pd F.exetech	To compare results of technical examination of the Polyptych in Perugia by Piero della Francesca with those from paintings in the National Gallery, London, by the same artist.	ARCHLAB 12_NG	3	Study of the detailed technical documentation on the works by Piero at the National Gallery in London, including reports (both conservation and scientific), images and other data, cross-sections, x-rays, infrareds etc. This has led to further collaboration on the analysis of the samples from the polyptych in Perugia.
Vince Van Thienen	1	ARC19_TS-CTP-UK	Thin section analysis of English clay tobacco pipes	ARCHLAB 11_BM	6	Thin section analysis of English clay tobacco pipes
Annalisa Krautheimer	3	ARC20_Oddy-Torium		ARCHLAB 11_BM	3	<i>Cancelled</i>
Hamada Kotb	1	ARC21_M URTECH	To study the technique of Byzantine mural paintings for some well-known painters at national and international levels. - To correlate between previous treatments and current conditions of selected churches - To gather information about consolidation treatments applied in Romania.	ARCHLAB 8_NIH	5	Study of detailed documentation reports on restoration works for several churches in UNESCO Heritage. Research in analytical studies by microscope and FTIR. On-site visits (see figure 2) and discussions with professionals.
Fifth call						
Nina Deleu	1	ARC 22_CUPRA	To study comparative documentation on occurrences of green copper sulphate pigments in 15 th and 16 th century Netherlandish painting	ARCHLAB 12_NG	6	The full technical documentation for around 15 National Gallery paintings in which copper sulphate had been confirmed as a pigment was studied, including the files, the paint cross-sections themselves, SEM-EDX and FTIR data. This was guided by NG scientists, who also discussed and exchanged knowledge on the research topic with the user group. As a result of this contact Marika Spring was invited to give a talk at a workshop on the same topic organized by the user group with the Slovakian National Gallery in Bratislava in October 2023.
Rossella Cavigli	3	ARC 24_MAMAT	To study technical documentation on Margarito d'Arezzo for research on his materials and techniques, to compare with studies of paintings from the same workshop in Italy	ARCHLAB 12_NG	4	The full technical documentation was consulted for the National Gallery 's Margarito d'Arezzo, The Virgin and Child Enthroned with Scenes of the Nativity and the Lives of Saints, from the 13 th century. The materials and techniques of this era in Italy have been studied far less than those of the 14 th century, therefore this was important comparative material for the user group's project on works by this artist in the Museo nazionale d'arte medievale e moderna in Arezzo. Reports, images, cross-sections, macro-XRF

						scanning and other non-invasive imaging were studied. Collaboration has continued as a result, with a joint conference in Italy in 2025 being planned.
Geert Van der Snickt	2	ARC 25_FLECAR BEL	Revealing the techniques of the Flemish Caravaggisti to check the impact of Caravaggio on Northern painters	ARCHLAB_5_OPD	3	Access to the documentation on the analyses carried out on two Caravaggio's paintings and one painting by De Ribera. Reviewing some cross-sections with optical microscope and taking new pictures. Check of the reports on two Rubens's painting and reviewing the cross-sections with optical microscope.
Lowie Vercruysee	3	ARC 25_FLECAR BEL	To compare the results of a study of a the technique and materials of a Flemish Caravaggisti painting with that of other contemporary Flemish paintings as well as Caravaggio and Caravaggisti in Italy to investigate any direct influences	ARCHLAB 12_NG	6	Documentation on analyses and technical imaging of three works by Caravaggio, and by Valentin (influenced by Caravaggio) were studied (cross sections, images, reports etc). After discussion with NG scientists about the user group's own results on the Flemish painting they had studied, other relevant documentation was suggested and consulted, including 6 Flemish works by Van Dyck, Rubens and Jordaens, and four works by the Utrecht Caravaggisti Honthorst and Terbrugghen
Sixth Call						
Romain Thomas	3	ARC 26_AORUM	To search for any easel painting, whatever its support (wood, canvas, stone or copper), whatever its technique (tempera, oil...) where the painter has used gold. In addition to gather as many pieces of information as possible about the gilding technique(s) employed by the painter in those paintings.	ARCHLAB_1_KIKIR PA	4	Consultation of the documentation concerning the analyses, the books with all the cross-sections, and the complete scientific reports of analyses of some artworks.
Romain Thomas	3		AORUM studies the uses of gold as a painting material at the time of its disaffection (16th and 17th c.), in a context of profound cultural and artistic changes. Within the accesses, searches for any easel painting, whatever its support (wood, canvas, stone or copper), whatever its technique (tempera, oil...) where the painter has used gold. It aims also to gather as many pieces of information as possible about the gilding technique(s) employed by the painter in those paintings.	ARCHLAB_9_IPCE	4	A great corpus of gilding paintings and sculptures form Spanish art has been studied at IPCE among the years. It was decided to focus on specific and very well studied cases due to the huge amount of records with the presence of gold: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedro Berruguete (1450 – 1504). A transitional style in Spain between gothic and Renaissance. He is considered by some as the first Renaissance painter in Spain. • "Triptico de la Resurrección" (c. XVI) attributed to Luis Velasco. • Altarpiece at Basílica de la Asunción de Nuestra Señora de Colmenar Viejo by Francisco Giralte(c. XVI). • Retablo Mayor de la Encarnación by Jose de la Torre (c. XVII) • Retablos laterales de la Iglesia de San Placido in Madrid by Pedro de la Torre (c. XVII)

						YouTube video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6CcTGoMl4wl
Jan van Maal	1	ARC 27_Durable Splendour	Access to archival records related to scientific research projects on Mosan and Limoges enamelwork, including the results of compositional analysis and radiography.	ARCHLAB_1_KIKIRPA	0	No reaction
Jan van Maal	1			ARCHLAB_11_BM	3	Access to archival records related to scientific research projects on Mosan and Limoges enamelwork, including the results of compositional analysis and radiography.
Jan van Maal	1			ARCHLAB_5_OPD	0	No reaction
Jan van Daal	1		The aim of Durable Splendour is to understand what the medieval people who commissioned, produced and experienced splendid art understood as 'durable'. Durable Splendour studies medieval patrons through commission contracts; artisanal techniques through art-technological recipe collections; and the experience of splendid art through a case study where we examine the materials and techniques of several surviving medieval artworks.	ARCHLAB_9_IPCE	4	<p>IPCE has a great variety of studies on reliquaries through the years. During the Access to IPCE Archives, the user could access to the correspondent information consisting on radiographies, chemical analysis, and restoration reports. Intense and fruitful discussions with the experts (chemists, image studies technicians and restorer) where crucial for the results of the access.</p> <p>Items involved on the access to IPCE where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arqueta-relicario con esmaltes de Limoges (c. XII-XIII) from Toledo Cathedral. • Saint Eugenio arqueta (c. XIII) from Toledo Cathedral. • Custodia-relicario (S.XIV) de los Corporales de la Iglesia Colegial de Daroca (Zaragoza). • Relicario (S.XIV) del Lignum Crucis (Catedral de Toledo) • Arqueta (S.XV) de San Martiriá del Monasterio de Sant Esteve de Banyoles (Gerona) • Custodia processional (S.XIV) de la Catedral de Santa María de Ibiza (Islas Baleares) <p>Youtube video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IIDT6ClnskE See figure 3.</p>

Seventh CALL						
Serena Benelli	1	ARC 30_DASA	The project aims to review the process and methods of archiving Cultural Heritage samples and records, to improve the preservation of digital and physical data related to the conservation and restoration of Historical and Artistic Heritage. The results would improve the management of the Gallone Archive of the Politecnico di Milano.	ARCHLAB _9_IPCE	6	Due to IPCE's experience in guarding and manage a Sample Archive since its creation, in the middle of XX century, and the collaboration in HSAI-ICCROM initiative, and interesting exchange between professionals with the same objectives came out from this ARCHLAB access. The user was especially interested on the materials and conditions to store microsamples, although other questions related to the trazability for all the generated information were addressed. Youtube video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aXbuK6KuRjY See figure 4
Marianne Moedlinger	2	ARC 31_DOTOPA	Comparing analytical data of copper-based doors of European churches	ARCHLAB _5_OPD	3	The access to the archival materials, helped us to reconstruct the "biographies" of two medieval bronze doors: San Zeno in Verona and Monte Sant'Angelo. The users had access to documents with the chemical analyses, which will be useful for comparison in the analysis of the XRF data that they achieved on these two doors and thus to verify their hypotheses on the production of the door. Particularly valuable was to find that the Opificio even still keeps samples of the patina of the door in Verona. These could be re-examined in a future project using more modern technologies, as they could provide important insights for the DOTOPA project, which primarily examined the surfaces using XRF. The samples from the Opificio are also important because the samples taken by the ICR (Istituto Centrale di Restauro, Rome) at the same time are no longer available. In addition, the Opificio archive still contains the photographs of the doors of the restoration period (1981), again very important for comparison.
Vanessa Antunes	1	ARC 32_FEMIN ART	The project is focused on the remarkable sevillian female artists of the Iberian Peninsula during the Golden Age. Specifically, into the techniques and materials employed by two exceptional artists, Josefa de Óbidos and Luisa Roldan, "La Roldana", who left an indelible mark on the artistic landscape of 17th-century Spain and Portugal.	ARCHLAB _9_IPCE	0	cancelled
Vladimir Bozinovic	1	ARC 34_SCC	To gather information about the relations between sculpture workshops employed in the construction of the Holy Trinity church	ARCHLAB 8_NIH	6	Consulting relevant literature on Cozia church, and archive photographs; Inspecting technical documentation containing restoration dairies and particularly architectural drawings from

			in Cozia monastery and Lazarica in Moravian Serbia. To establish more exact insight into the movement of Moravian carvers.			1928, 1930, 1944, 1964, and 1966. Analysis of the iconography of depicted ornaments on-site. (see figure 5)
Beatrice Ciuta	1	ARC 35_SIAB-REGIA	"The aim of this project is the scientific investigation of the archaeological bread-like objects discovered at Sarmizegetusa Regia, Romania. These investigations are among the few carried out in Romania on fragments of carbonized bread-like objects. The site of Sarmizegetusa Regia, located in Grădiștea de Munte village, in Orastie Mountains (Hunedoara county), was the capital of the Dacian state, and therefore of great importance in the ancient history of Romania."	ARCHLAB_13_Historic England	4	"The project was centred on identifying the nature of carbonized organic remains at Dacian sites, particularly to determine if they were remnants of ancient bread. We conducted extensive examinations, including microscopic microstructure analysis of cereal products, content analysis, and the capturing of detailed photographs. Our research also involved comparing our findings with pre-existing information from the ARCHLAB archive. Utilizing advanced technologies provided by ARCHLAB, such as the 3D digital Keyence microscope, SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy), and XRF (X-Ray Fluorescence) spectroscopy, we gained new insights into the dietary and agricultural practices of ancient Dacia. Our analysis of organic fragments from Sarmizegetusa Regia and Simleul Silvaniei (Dacian sites from Romania) indicated the use of cereals in porridge preparation, as well as other food preparation techniques. A significant focus of our study was to differentiate food fragments from charcoal and other organic materials, an essential step in isolating relevant remains for our research. We applied various techniques and technologies to categorize the samples based on visible particles and porosity, a journal publication is planned." (see figure 6)
Amandine Colignon	2	ARC 36_MeTox IT2	To assess the presence and distribution of metal oxalates in Italian tempera paintings to be compared to oil paintings	ARCHLAB 5_OPD	6	Selection of a corpus of tempera samples in cross-sections for FTIR mapping and Raman analysis to check the presence and distribution of metal oxalates
Suzanne REUS	3	ARC 38_U POP	Study of the degradation of Prussian blue in painting from the 18th to the 20th century	ARCHLAB 3_C2RMF	5	38 files of works consulted (notably laboratory reports), 2 rare books from the reserve, several scientific articles. Time for discussion with scientists from the painting group of the C2RMF Research department who worked on Prussian blue as part of a research project
Suzanne REUS	3	ARC 38_U POP	Study of the degradation of Prussian blue in painting from the 18th to the 20th century	ARCHLAB 12_NG	4	Consulted large number of files for paintings in which Prussian blue had been identified, concentrating especially on works by Van Gogh and contemporaries, but also studying documentation on earlier works where Prussian blue had been used almost alone

						(eg. Gainsborough). Study of high-resolution images, photomicrographs, paint cross sections, EDX spectra, FTIR spectra etc. Time for discussion with scientists from the NG scientific department who worked on Prussian blue as part of a past research project.
Katharina Habinger		ARC 39_CoMI	The project examines the colour changes of modern oil colours in paintings by Maria Lassnig (1919– 2014). Gaining access to the transnational platform ARCHLAB would elevate these aspects and expand the scientific relevance of this project. Additionally, examinations with the help of experimental methods will foster the approach	ARCHLAB 6_RCE	4	Exploring the reference collection of the RCE. Checking the archives. Presentation of the project and discussions with RCE scientists
Martina BEZOUSK OVA	3	ARC 40_ED Rev NGP	Study of works attributed to Delacroix at the National Gallery Prague: comparison with C2RMF analysis data	ARCHLAB 3_C2RM F	5	Consultation of 43 files of Delacroix's works and 25 x-rays, around ten books and periodicals from the library
Pınar ÖZÜKURT	1	ARC 42_ATSOP	Shortly after the beginning of farming in the Fertile Crescent, farmers had to face a major cold spell that cooled temperatures in the Middle East by 2oC. Understanding how lifeways were reorganized as a result of this climate change is a major challenge for archaeologists. Oxygen isotope ratios ($\delta^{18}O$) in archaeological tooth enamel are a powerful proxy for climate stability or change because they archive temperature and precipitation like ice or marine cores do --incrementally, in the case of teeth, throughout the formation of the tooth enamel during animal's early years in life. The added value of teeth is that it also gives information about how animals move or are moved by humans through landscapes, for example between different altitudes with large temperature differences.	ARCHLAB 7_RUG	11	The user was here to learn how to sample sheep and goat tooth enamel. The specimens from a key and unique archaeological site in Cappadocia, Turkey dating to before, during and after this period have been acquired by RUG a while ago. The samples will be measured for their oxygen isotope compositions. Results will inform how farming life changed this millennium in terms of climate-mobility-food production interactions.
Anastasiia Korokhina	2	ARC 43_WAYF	Study of 54 thin sections from the Sanctuary of Agios Lot at the Deir 'Ain 'Abata Monastery in Jordan	ARCHLAB _11_BM	6	Study of 54 thin sections from the Sanctuary of Agios Lot at the Deir 'Ain 'Abata Monastery in Jordan

Amelia Hammond	2	ARC 44_VITAL Cu	Understanding the impact of conservation treatments of the past on cupreous archeological objects	ARCHLAB 5_OPD	3	Investigation of the digital conservation and analytical records on archaeological copper-based alloys, discussion with the conservators on past and current treatments and their possible impact of the corrosion behavior of the objects' surface.
	3		The aim of this project is to use knowledge found in objects, treatments, and archives available in the present to understand conservation treatments of the past, specifically on cupreous archaeological finds. Information about cupreous objects collected from archaeological sites is vital to a well-formed understanding of material cultural heritage.	ARCHLAB 13_HE	5	Consultation of the archives to compare past and current treatments of cupreous archaeological finds. Visits to Portsmouth Historic Dockyard to view consult with experts on objects/ records from the Mary Rose and other shipwrecks. Visit (to Southend-on Sea Museum to consult objects /records/ curators from the wreck of the London. The objects from London were conserved at Historic England Laboratories. (see figure 7)

KPI's

Following results relate to the KPI's defined in the Grant Agreement. The results related to M1-M27 are marked in grey.

KPI Demand % request vs slots	1st Call	2nd Call	3rd Call	4th Call	5th Call	6th Call	7th Call	AVERAGE
ARCHLAB	1	0,27	0,72	0,45	0,55	0,91	1,27	0,738571

SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE

KPI_{E01}. Yearly number of users requests	Call 1	Call 2	Call 3	Call 4	Call 5	Call 6	Call 7
ARCHLAB	26	5	13	11	16	11	25

KPI_{E02}. Yearly number of granted accesses	Call 1		Call 2		Call 3		Call 4		Call 5		Call 6		Call 7	
	31/01/2021		30/06/2021		30/11/2021		29/04/2022		30/09/2022		28/02/2023		30/06/2023	
	Projects granted	Users	Projects granted	Users	Projects	User Group no.								
ARCHLAB	5	9	2	5	3	8	5	17	4	16	2	7	12	28

ENHANCING COLLABORATION IN EUROPE

KPI_{E03}. Share of EU users	Call 1	Call 2	Call 3	Call 4	Call 5	Call 6	Call 7
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	31/01/2021	30/06/2021	30/11/2021	29/04/2022	30/09/2022	28/02/2023	30/06/2023
ARCHLAB	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,44

FACILITATING INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

KPI_{E04} . Share of users from outside the EU	Call 1	Call 2	Call 3	Call 4	Call 5	Call 6	Call 7
	31/01/2021	30/06/2021	30/11/2021	29/04/2022	30/09/2022	28/02/2023	30/06/2023
ARCHLAB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,56

ADVANCING RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT IN ARCHLAB

Each of the work packages governing the access platforms has a dedicated task on data management, which is supported by and is supporting the networking task 6.3 on interoperability. Task 2.4 had three main goals:

1. Establishing a uniform approach to data management: Task 2.4 aimed to develop a uniform approach to data management across access providers for individual access projects. This involved addressing issues such as intellectual property rights (IPR), data management, and data re-use in consultation with users. The goal was to ensure consistency in how data are managed and utilized across different institutions and countries involved in the project.
2. Enhancing findability of data: Another objective was to enhance the findability of data held in archives and related to objects and crafts. This involved establishing steps to improve the accessibility and discoverability of data in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. Measures included agreeing on what data to gather, creating forms or templates for this purpose, and implementing a standardized and semantically mapped cataloging system based on metadata.
3. Exploring future digital research resources: Task 2.4 also aimed to identify possible pathways for future digital research resources within the E-RIHS DIGILAB platform or E-RIHS' digital infrastructure. This involved investigating opportunities among providers for the development of the platform, including ways to digitize and make accessible digital data currently only accessible by visiting institutions, leading towards a digital ARCHLAB access.

These efforts are crucial for improving the usability and impact of the data held within ARCHLAB for heritage science research. This aligns with the evolution to anchor ARCHLAB within the developing DIGILAB and digital infrastructure of E-RIHS.

In terms of data management, the data types and requirements are significantly different from those in FIXLAB and MOLAB. Firstly, the focus is on consulting existing data (background data) that exists in the archives of the ARCHLAB providers. This data is the property of the provider and/or third parties. Often, in the process of preparing the visit, the provider updates certain data (e.g. new digital microscopy images) on their own initiative or in collaboration with the user during the visit. This results in consulted pre-existing, consulted new, and new derived data, each governed by different terms. Data created using IPERION HS financing must be open and made available (e.g. on Zenodo or an institutional repository).

To gain a clearer understanding of the types of data consulted and created, and the terms under which they can be used, a form titled "Overview of Consulted and Prepared Data" was created. This form guides ARCHLAB providers and users through data management requirements outlined in the IPERION HS Data Management Plan. It captures essential information about consulted and generated data during access provisions, facilitating learning and improvement in data management

practices. The form was completed by several access providers following an access to collect information.

A key aspect of Task 2.4 is related to IPERION HS's Data Management Plan (DMP) [1], which was written as part of the activities of Task 6.3 (Interoperability) and will serve as the basis for the DMP of the future E-RIHS ERIC. The data management tasks in the work packages of the three access platforms contributed to the DMP. The information collected using the form was used as a basis to check the applicability of the DMP. Additionally, the form aimed to provide guidelines and best practices to ARCHLAB providers to manage consulted and generated data according to the DMP.

While the form was instrumental in obtaining a better understanding of the consulted and generated data in ARCHLAB accesses, it left providers with text boxes to describe the data and terms in their own words and structure. Consequently, the initial goal to publish non-machine-actionable forms of the test phase on Zenodo as a trace of the consulted data was considered futile. Evolving into E-RIHS ERIC, a standardised and machine-readable documentation system is required.

Task 6.3 on interoperability played a complementary role in advancing research data management in ARCHLAB. Besides the development of the project's DMP, the task focused on modeling the complete data lifecycle of data in E-RIHS [2], including efforts to explore practical approaches to interoperability and define metadata required for achieving acceptable levels of interoperability. This includes ARCHLAB, and the data collected in the forms are used to evaluate the models.

The models are being converted into JSON Schema files that define the structure and organization of data with its para- and metadata. As a side effect, these schemas can be used to generate web forms that help providers and users document and store their data in a consistent and harmonized way. Although Task 6.3 was a networking task, a pilot instance of Cordra was set up [3]. This is an open-source software solution for managing digital objects, based on JSON Schema, which could become essentially the metadata storage engine or knowledge base for the future E-RIHS ERIC. This will replace the forms, rendering the data and metadata machine-actionable and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable).

The development of the schemas and the implementation of the knowledge base have been handed over to E-RIHS IP, in preparation for the launch of the ERIC.

CONCLUSION

22 projects were received during the last 3 calls, of which 1 was rejected, due to ineligibility issues or too low quality. 21 proposals have been submitted to the Peer Review Panel, out of which 16 have been selected corresponding to 29 accesses (some proposals requested access to archives of more than one provider). The origin of the selected proposals is quite representative of the European diversity, with a panel of 12 nationalities, besides Switzerland and Hong Kong.

For the entire project (M1-M48) Of the 29 selected proposals and 44 access visits, 37 access visits have been carried out corresponding to 163 access days. The number of access days (163) is below the objective of 341 access days at M48 (48%).

From the received feedback, users are satisfied about the support offered and the fulfillment of expectations of the offered accesses.

A document was setup that enables the management of the consulted and, eventually, generated data to be implemented for the accesses that took place. It captures essential information about consulted and generated data during access provisions, facilitating learning and improvement in data management practices. The form was completed by several access providers following an access to collect information.

Besides, models have been developed that define the structure and organization of data with its para- and metadata as solution for managing digital objects, which could become essentially the knowledge base for the future E-RIHS ERIC.

Figure 2: ARC21_MURTECH, NIH, on site visits

Figure 3 ARC27_Durable Splendour_IPCE

Figure 4: ARC30_DASA_IPCE

Figure 5: ARC 34_SCC, archives NIH

Figure 6: ARC35_SIAB-REGIA, Historic England

Figure 7: ARC 44_VITAL Cu, Historic England

References

- [1] Joseph Padfield, Laura Benassi, Marta Castillejo, D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS, 2021, doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4541267](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4541267)
- [2] Joseph Padfield, Wim Fremout, Wolfgang Schmidle, Sophia Sotiropoulou, Interim report on documentation of instrument parameters and analysis protocols across access platforms, and metadata requirements, 2022, doi:[10.5281/zenodo.7101169](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101169)
- [3] E-RIHS Knowledge Base, <https://data.e-rihs.io>

ANNEXE

Table: Researcher Information

RESEARCHER				EMPLOYING ORGANIZATION/ HOME INSTITUTION			OTHER INFORMATION	
First Name	Last Name	Nationality	Gender	Name	Legal status ¹	country	User project acronym	Activity domain ²
Lafarga	Manuel	ES	Male	Conservatorio Superior de Música de Alicante	RES	ES	MRVWCXR	Humanities Information and Communication technologies
Camarero Manzanero	Jorge	ES	Male	Conservatorio Superior de Música de Alicante	RES	ES		
Sanz	Penelope	ES	Female					
Chafer Bixquert	Teresa	ES	Female	Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV)	UNI	ES		
Roig Picazo	Pilar	ES	Female	Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV)	UNI	ES		
Fenlon	Iain	GB	Male	University of Cambridge	UNI	GB		
Asensi Seva	Vicente	ES	Male	Conservatorio Superior de Música de Alicante	RES	ES		
Llimera Dus	Vicent	ES	Male	Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) & Conservatorio Superior de Música de València	UNI	ES		
Alejano Casillas	Javier	ES	Male					
Grazzi	Francesco	IT	Male	CNR - IFAC	RES	IT		
Cantini	Francesco	IT	Male	Università di Firenze - Dipartimento di Fisica	UNI	IT		

Antunes	Vanesa	PT	Female	Instituto de História da Arte da Faculdade de Letras da Universidade de Lisboa (ARTIS-IHA)	UNI	PT	ZAINTIBERIA	Humanities Material Science
Palladino	Nicole	IT	Female	C2RMF	RES	FR	ZOoMM	Chemistry Material Science Physics
Salvant	Johana	FR	Female	C2RMF	RES	FR		
Cardinali	Marco	IT	Male	Università della Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli"	UNI	IT	IMAGO	Humanities
Cerasuolo	Angela	IT	Female	Museo e Real Bosco di Capodimonte	RES	IT	CAMPUS	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics
Zeza	Andrea	IT	Male	Università degli Studi della Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli"	UNI	IT		
Damiani	Suzana	HR	Female	University of Zagreb, Academy of Fine Arts	UNI	HR	DiODuCat - A	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Zeman	Maja	HR	Female	University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences	UNI	HR		
Martinović	Ivan Vanja	HR	Male	University of Zagreb, Academy of Fine Arts	UNI	HR		
Gherardi	Francesca	IT	Female	Historic England	RES	GB		
Sarah	Paynter	GB	Female	Historic England	RES	GB	ARTDEICS	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Thomas	Romain	FR	Male	Paris Nanterre University	UNI	FR	AORUM	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics Social sciences
Le Hô	Anne-Solenn	FR	Female	Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées de France (C2RMF)	RES	FR		
Dubost	Marie	FR	Female	Atelier de la feuille d'or	SME	FR		
Korro	Miren Jaione	ES	Female	University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU)	UNI	ES	MANAGECO NSERV	Humanities Information and Communication technologies

Świtczak	Paula Karina	PL	Female	Nicolaus Copernicus University	UNI	PL	MET_HER	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Tomassetti	Maria Cristina	IT	Female	Galleria Nazionale dell'Umbria	OTH	IT	PDF.exe.tech.	Humanities
Picchiarelli	Veruska	IT	Female	Galleria Nazionale dell'Umbria	OTH	IT		
Costantini	Daniele	IT	Male	Galleria Nazionale dell'Umbria	OTH	IT		
Steger	Simon	AT	Male	Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design	UNI	DE	Oddytorium	Chemistry Earth Sciences & Environment Material Science
Hristova	Valentina	BG	Female	Université Paris Nanterre	UNI	FR	AORUM	Chemistry Humanities Information and Communication technologies Material Science Physics Social sciences
Albrecht	Marya	NL	Female	Atelier Albrecht Schilderijenrestauratie	SME	NL	EMPTY	Humanities
Daughertry	Melissa	NL	Female	Restauratieatelier Daugherty	SME	NL		
Van Gerven	Gert	NL	Male	Studio Van Gerven	SME	NL		
Mederos-Henry	Francisco	BE	Male	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage	RES	BE	MetOx-IT	Chemistry Humanities
Sanyova	Jana	SK	Female	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage	RES	BE		
Collignon	Amandine	BE	Female	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage	RES	BE		
Quintero Balbás	Diego Iván	MX	Male	National Institute of Optics	RES	IT		
Van Thienen	Vince	BE	Male	Ghent University	UNI	BE	TS-CTP-UK	Earth Sciences & Environment Humanities
Krautheimer	Anna Lisa	DE	Female	Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design	UNI	DE	Oddytorium	Chemistry Material Science
Krekel	Christoph	DE	Male	Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design	UNI	DE		
Eggert	Gerhard	DE	Male	Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design	UNI	DE		
Kotb	Hameda	EG	Male	The University of Bologna	UNI	IT	MURTECH	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Social sciences

Van der Snickt	Geert	BE	Male	University of Antwerp	UNI	BE	CUPRA	Conservation-Restoration Chemistry
Deleu	Nina	BE	Female	University of Antwerp	UNI	BE		
Janssens	Koen	BE	Male	University of Antwerp	UNI	BE		
Sanyova	Jana	SK	Female	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA)	RES	BE		
Cavigli	Rossella	IT	Female	MNAMM – Direzione regionale musei della Toscana - MIC	RES	IT	MAMAT	Chemistry Conservazione Art History
Piqué	Francesca	IT	Female	SUSPI-University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland	UNI	CH		
Tedbury	Imogen	GB	Female	formerly National Gallery, London	RES	GB		
Van der Snickt	Geert	BE	Male	University of Antwerp	UNI	BE	FLECARMEL	Conservation Art Sciences
Vercruyssen	Lowie	BE	Male	University of Antwerp	UNI	BE		
Harth	Astrid	BE	Female	City University of Hong Kong	UNI	HK		
Van Dam	Frederica	BE	Female	Museum of Fine Arts Ghent (MSK)	PRV	BE		
Derks	Kirsten	NL	Female	University of Antwerp	UNI	BE		
Pinto	Ariane	FR	Female	FSP - C2RMF	OTH	FR	AORUM	Art History Conservation Science Physical-chemistry
Betelu	Claire	FR	Female	Université Paris 1	UNI	FR		
Debrie	Juliette	FR	Female	Laboratoire d'archéologie moléculaire et structurale	RES	FR		
Van Daal	Jan	NL	Male	Utrecht University	UNI	NL	Durable Splendour	Heritage Science Technical Art History
Joosten	Ineke	NL	Female	Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands (RCE)	RES	NL		
Bol	Marjolijn	NL	Female	Utrecht University	UNI	NL		
Radvan	Alexandru	RO	Male	National University of	UNI	RO	OKNOS	

				Arts from Bucharest				
Benelli	Seren a	IT	Female	Politecnico di Milano	UNI	IT	DASA	
Moedlinger	Maria nne	AT	Female	IMAREAL, University of Salzburg	UNI	AT	DOTOPA	Art History
Utz	Judith	DE	Female	IMAREAL, University of Salzburg	UNI	AT		
Antunes	Vanes sa	PT	Female	Faculdade de letras da Universidade de Lisboa	UNI	PT	FEMINART	
Ciocanu	Sergiu s	MD	Male	Technical University of Moldova	UNI	MD	STEASB	
Bozinovic	Vladi mir	RS	Male	Republic Institute for the Protection of Cultural Monuments	RES	RS	SCC	
Ciuta	Elena-Beatri ce	RO	Female	1 Decembrie 1918 University from Alba Iulia	UNI	RO	SIAB-REGIA	
Colignon	Aman dine	BE	Female	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage	RES	BE	MetOx-IT2	Chemistry Art Conservation-Restoration
Mederos-Henry	Franci sco	BE	Male	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage	RES	BE		
Quintero Balbas	Diego Ivan	MX	Male	National Institute of Optics	RES	IT		
Striova	Jana	CZ	Female	National Institute of Optics	RES	IT		
Retournard	Emelin e	FR	Female	Université Clermont-Auvergne	UNI	FR		
Reus	Suzan ne	NL	Female	University of Amsterdam, Van 't Hoff Institute for Molecular Sciences	UNI	NL	U-POP	Chemistry
Van den Berg	Klaas Jan	NL	Male	University of Amsterdam, conservation & restoration of cultural heritage	UNI	NL		
Van Bommel	Maart en	NL	Male	University of Amsterdam, conservation & restoration of	UNI	NL		

				cultural heritage				
Habiger	Katharina	AT	Female	Atelier Walde	OTH	AT	CoML	
Bezoušková	Martina	CZ	Female	National Gallery Prague	RES	CZ	ED Rev NGP	Chemistry Conservation
Antušková	Václava	CZ	Female	National Gallery Prague	RES	CZ		
Horvathová	Marie	CZ	Female	National Gallery Prague	RES	CZ		
Özüktür	Pinar	TR	Female	Istanbul University	UNI	TR	ATSOTP	
Korokhina	Anastasiia	UA	Female	Leibniz Institute for the History and Culture of Eastern Europe (GWZO)	RES	DE	WAYF	Archeology
Khamai	Natalia	UA	Female	Leibniz Institute for the History and Culture of Eastern Europe (GWZO)	RES	DE		
Hammond	Amelina	US	Prefer not to say	University of Amsterdam	UNI	NL	VITAI Cu	Conservation
Davidowitz	Tamar	NL	Female	University of Amsterdam / Rijksmuseum	UNI	NL		
Joosten	Ineke	NL	Female	Rijksdienst voor cultureel erfgoed	RES	NL		

1 UNI- University and other higher education organizations

RES- Public research organization (including international and private research organizations controlled by a public authority)

SME- Small or Medium Enterprises

PRV- Other Industrial and/or profit Private organization

OTH- Other organization not fitting in one of the above category

2 Chemistry

Earth sciences and Environment

Energy

Engineering and Technology

Humanities

Information and Communication Technologies

Life sciences and Biotech

Material sciences

Mathematics

Physics